

A UNIQUE COLLECTION OF LITERARY WORKS OFTEN CONFUSED (PART-II)

Mr. Sanjeev Kumar Bansal ,

M.A. (English); M.ED.; NET (English & Education) ,

Assistant Teacher, U.P.S.- Soorajpur,

V.K.- Amaria, Distt. - Pilibhit, U.P.-262001

Abstract

After reading British, Indian, American & some Commonwealth literature, I found huge works scattered here and there in various books which sometimes confuses the readers/competitors in the examination hall due to the inherent similarities in these entitled works. To avoid this type of common confusion, I planned to search and arrange the important works first, their similarity wise and their frequency wise and then I compiled an exhaustive list of these selected works to facilitate the learners to make clear cut distinction among the various titles of the literary works. My research paper is based on the principles of effective teaching- learning and effective memorization. My research paper is also entertaining since it enhances the concept of -Learning is Fun. This is my attempt in the pedagogy of teaching-learning of English Literature. I hope my collection will help the students as well as teachers who can frame confusing Multiple Choice Questions (M.C.Q) to refine their learning and also to check the depth of students' learning. This research paper will be more useful to those who have read at least once The History of English Literature. It will make the readers to realize similar titles of the different literary works as dissimilar and vice-versa. I have divided my research paper in two parts, as Part-I & Part-II. This paper is the continuance of my previous research paper & there are around 850 literary works included in it which readers often confused and these works are not the last but the least.

Major Keywords: *Under, Green Wood, Tree, Leaves, Garden, Wind, Dust, Summer, Pleasures, Zoo, Doctor, Heart, Eye, Anatomy, World, Adventures, Road, Travels, Journey, Maps, Fair, Way, Pilgrim, Directions, Tower, White, Black, Red, Silver, Golden, House, Room, Mermaid,*

Girls, Love, Dance, Rose, Ring, Time, Numbers (2,3,4,7,), Tales, Moon, Books, Chapter, End , etc.

Introduction:

This part of my research paper also covers the literary works from British, American, Indian & some Commonwealth literature which readers often confuses. As we knew very well that there are three levels of learning viz. Memory level, Understanding level & Reflective level of learning. Usually readers used to memorize the literary works that is essential but this memorization must be supplemented with proper understanding .That's why , my research paper is associated with higher levels of learning i.e. Understanding & Reflective Levels of learning. I have tried my best in sequencing the selected literary works which readers often confuse. I strived hard to give a sort of continuity to my collection so that the readers may easily associate the various works of this collection in their mind. I have divided my research paper in two parts, as Part-I & Part-II. I am quite sure that after reading the both parts of this paper, readers will be able to differentiate & integrate the often confused literary works in an entertaining way. In my previous research paper "A Unique Collection of Literary Works Often Confused (Part-I)", you have read around 750 literary works which readers often confuses. Now, in the continuance of the previous research paper about 850 literary works are included in this Part-II, which are given below with their keywords highlighted in the italics.

Literary Works:-

<i>Under The Green Wood Tree</i>	– Thomas Hardy
<i>Under tones of War</i>	- Edmund Blunden
<i>Under the Western Eyes</i>	- Joseph Conrad
<i>Under Kilmanjaro</i>	- Ernest Hemingway
<i>Under the Banyan Tree</i>	- R. K. Narayan
<i>Under woods</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
<i>Under woods</i>	- Ben Jonson
<i>Under Ben Bulben</i>	–W. B. Yeats

✚ The Causarina <i>Tree</i>	- W.S. Maugham
✚ The Friendly <i>Tree</i>	- C. Day Lewis
✚ On Killing a <i>Tree</i>	- Gieve Patel
✚ Granny's <i>Tree</i> Climbing	- Ruskin Bond
✚ Our <i>Trees</i> Still Grow in Dehra	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The Coral <i>Tree</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ A Witness <i>Tree</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ The Wishing <i>Tree</i>	- W. Faulkner
✚ The Poison <i>Tree</i>	- B. C. Chatterjee
✚ The Holy <i>Tree</i>	- Robert Southey
✚ <i>Poison</i> Belt	- A. C. Doyle
✚ The <i>Scarlet</i> <i>Tree</i>	- Osbert Sitwell
✚ The <i>Scarlet</i> Letter	- N. Hawthorne
✚ The Wanting <i>Seed</i>	- Anthony Burgess
✚ Those Barren <i>Leaves</i>	- A. L. Huxley
✚ Faded <i>Leaves</i>	- Matthew Arnold
✚ <i>Leaves</i> in the <i>Wind</i>	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ Two <i>Leaves</i> and a Bud	- M. R. Anand
✚ The Trembling of a <i>Leaf</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ <i>Leaves</i> of Grass	- Walt Whitman
✚ The Peacock <i>Garden</i>	- Anita Desai
✚ Of King's Treasuries & of Queen's <i>Garden</i>	- John Ruskin
✚ A Child's <i>Garden</i> of Verses	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ The <i>Garden</i> of Cyrus	- Sir Thomas Browne
✚ The <i>Garden</i> of Love	- William Blake
✚ The <i>Garden</i> of Eden	- Ernest Hemingway
✚ <i>East</i> <i>Wind</i>	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>West</i> <i>Wind</i>	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>South</i> <i>Wind</i>	- Norman Douglas
✚ The <i>Wind</i> Among the Reeds	- W. B. Yeats

✚ Windsor Forest	- John Denham
✚ Leaves in the Wind	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ Wind Falls	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ A High Wind in Jamaica	- Richard Hughes
✚ From the Four Winds	- John Galsworthy
✚ Not I	- Samuel Beckett
✚ Not I , But the Wind	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ The Devil's Wind	- Manohar Malgaonkar
✚ The Wind hover	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ Heat & Dust	- R. P. Jhabvala
✚ A Handful of Dust	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ Purple Dust	- Sean O'casey
✚ Flags in the Dust	- William Faulkner
✚ Intruder in the Dust	- William Faulkner
✚ Ethics of the Dust	- John Ruskin
✚ Dust on the Mountains	- Ruskin Bond
✚ Rain in the Mountains : Notes From The Himalayas	- Ruskin Bond
✚ Mountains of Dehra	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The Cycle of Spring	- R. N. Tagore
✚ The Torrents of Spring	- Ernest Hemmingway
✚ Spring & Fall	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ The Dangerous Summer	- Ernest Hemmingway
✚ Where Shall We Go this Summer ?	- Anita Desai
✚ After Many a Summer	- Aldous Huxley
✚ Seven Summers	- M. R. Anand
✚ Summer in Calcutta	- Kamla Das
✚ Summer Lightning	- P. G. Wodehouse
✚ Last Summer	- Boris Pasternak
✚ Summers Last Will	- Thomas Nashe

✚ <i>Midsummer's Night Dream</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ <i>Winter's Tale</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ <i>Pleasure City</i>	- Kamala Markandaya
✚ <i>The Pleasure Dome</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Pleasures of Melancholy</i>	- Warbon
✚ <i>The Pleasures of Imagination</i>	- Mark Akenside
✚ <i>On the Pleasures of Imagination</i>	- Addison
✚ <i>Pleasures of Hope</i>	- Thomas Campbell
✚ <i>Pleasures of Memory</i>	- Samuel Rogers
✚ <i>The Pleasures of Steamers</i>	- Andrew Motion
✚ <i>The Pleasures of Poetry</i>	- Edith Sitwell
✚ <i>On Reason & Imagination</i>	- W. Hazlitt
✚ <i>The Passetime of Pleasure</i>	- Stephen Hawes
✚ <i>The London Zoo</i>	- C. H. Sisson
✚ <i>The Zoo Story</i>	- Edward Albee
✚ <i>A Man in the Zoo</i>	- Garnett
✚ <i>My Butterfly</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ <i>The Brass Butterfly</i>	- William Golding
✚ <i>The Breaking of a Butterfly</i>	- H. A. Jones
✚ <i>The Broken Wing</i>	- Sarojini Naidu
✚ <i>Broken Ties</i>	- R. N. Tagore
✚ <i>Broken Nest</i>	- R. N. Tagore
✚ <i>The Broken Heart</i>	- John Ford
✚ <i>Sunlight on a Broken Column</i>	- Attia Hosain
✚ <i>The Caged Skylark</i>	- G. M. Hopkins
✚ <i>To a Skylark</i>	- P. B. Shelley
✚ <i>The Parrot in the Cage</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>The Parrot's Death</i>	- P. Lal
✚ <i>Cat on a Hot Tin Roof</i>	- Tennessee Williams
✚ <i>The Cat in the Hat</i>	- Dr. Seuss

✚ Of <i>Mice & Men</i>	- John Steinbeck
✚ The City <i>Mouse & the Country Mouse</i>	- Matthew Prior
✚ <i>Cat & Mouse</i>	- Gunter Grass
✚ The <i>Cat & the Moon</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The <i>Cat & Shakespeare</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ On the Death of a Favourite <i>Cat</i>	- Thomas Gray
✚ On the Death of a Mad <i>Dog</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ <i>Isle of Dogs</i>	- Nashe & Marston
✚ All About a <i>Dog</i>	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ To Say Nothing of the <i>Dog</i>	- J. K. Jerome
✚ The <i>Dog</i> Beneath the Skin	- Auden & Isherwood
✚ <i>Dog</i> Years	- Gunter Grass
✚ The <i>Scorpion</i> God	- William Golding
✚ The Day of the <i>Scorpion</i>	- Paul Scott
✚ Night of the <i>Scorpion</i>	- Nissim Ezekiel
✚ The <i>Cow</i> of the Barricades & Other Stories	- Raja Rao
✚ The Old <i>Woman & the Cow</i> or Gauri	- M. R. Anand
✚ The Valley of <i>Bones</i>	- Anthony Powell
✚ The <i>Bone</i> People	- Keri Hulme
✚ The <i>Doctor's</i> Dilemma	- G. B. Shaw
✚ <i>Doctor</i> Zhivago	- Boris Pasternak
✚ <i>Doctor</i> Faustus	- Christopher Marlowe
✚ The English <i>Patient</i>	- Michael Ondaatjee
✚ A Suitable Case for <i>Treatment</i>	- David Mercer
✚ Island of <i>Dr. Moreau</i>	- H. G. Wells
✚ <i>Dr. Jekyll & Mr. Hyde</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ Epistle to <i>Dr. Arbuthnot</i>	- Alexander Pope
✚ <i>Nude Therapy</i>	- Saros Cowasjee
✚ <i>Small Remedies</i>	- Shashi Deshpandey

✚ Desperate Remedies	- Thomas Hardy
✚ Love in the Time of Cholera	- G. G. Marquez
✚ Religio Medici	- Sir Thomas Browne
✚ Religio Laici	- John Dryden
✚ The Doctrine of Heart	- Annie Besant
✚ The New Inn or the Light Heart	- Ben Jonson
✚ Heart of Darkness	- Joseph Conrad
✚ The Heart of the Matter	- Graham Greene
✚ The Big Heart	- M. R. Anand
✚ Heart Break House	- G. B .Shaw
✚ The Heart of Midlothian	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The Land of Heart's Desire	- W. B. Yeats
✚ Heartsease & the Daisy Chain	-C. M. Yonge
✚ The Heart's Journey	- Siegfried Sassoon
✚ The Broken Heart	- John Ford
✚ A Severed Head	- Miss Iris Murdoch
✚ The Handmaid's Tale	- Harold Pinter
✚ The Handmaid's Tale	- Margaret Atwood
✚ The Hand of Ethelbeta : A Comedy in Chapters	- Thomas Hardy
✚ Left Hand, Right Hand	- Osbert Sitwell
✚ A Handful of Dust	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ A Pair of Blue Eyes	- Thomas Hardy
✚ Under the Western Eyes	- Joseph Conrad
✚ The Bluest Eye	- Toni Morrison
✚ Eyeless in Gaza	- A. L. Huxley
✚ The Eyes Have It	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The Blind Assassin	- Margaret Atwood
✚ The Anatomy of the World	- John Donne
✚ Anatomy of Melancholy	- Robert Burton
✚ The Anatomy of Frustration	- H. G. Wells

+ <i>Anatomy of Wit</i>	- John Lyly
+ <i>Anatomy of Criticism</i>	- Northrop Frye
+ <i>Anatomy of Absurdity</i>	- Thomas Nashe
+ <i>Anatomy of a Flawed Inheritance</i>	- J. N. Dixit
+ <i>The Brave New World</i>	- A. L. Huxley
+ <i>It is Fine World</i>	- Robert Lynd
+ <i>The World's Body</i>	- J. C. Ransom
+ <i>The War of the Worlds</i>	- H. G. Wells
+ <i>The Citizen of the World</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
+ <i>The End of the World</i>	- Gordon Bottomley
+ <i>The End of the World</i>	- Lascelles Abercrombie
+ <i>The Playboy of the Western World</i>	- J. M. Synge
+ <i>The World of the Story Teller</i>	- R. K. Narayan
+ <i>World Within World</i>	- Stephen Spender
+ <i>The Acceptance World</i>	- Anthony Powell
+ <i>Starting Point</i>	- C. Day Lewis
+ <i>Point Counter Point</i>	- A. L. Huxley
+ <i>A Start in Life</i>	- Alan Silbitoe
+ <i>Beginning of the Beginning</i>	- Acharya Rajneesh
+ <i>End & Beginning</i>	- John Masefield
+ <i>Prelude to Adventure</i>	- Hugh Walpole
+ <i>The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn</i>	- Mark Twain
+ <i>The Adventures of Tom Sawyer</i>	- Mark Twain
+ <i>Adventures of Ulysses</i>	- C. Lamb
+ <i>Adventures of Robinson Crusoe</i>	- Daniel Defoe
+ <i>Adventures of Sally</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
+ <i>Adventures of Sherlock Holmes</i>	- Sir A. C. Doyle
+ <i>The Adventure of the Black Lady</i>	- Mrs. Aphra Behn
+ <i>The Adventures of Gentleman</i>	- Edwin L. Bulwer

✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of Master F. J.	- G. Gascoigne
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of J. Andrews	- Henry Fielding
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of David Simple	- Sarah Fielding
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of Peregrine Pickle	- Tobias Smollett
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of Ferdinand Count Fathom	- Tobias Smollett
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of <i>Roderick</i> Random	- Tobias Smollett
✚ The <i>Adventures</i> of Sir Lancelot Greaves	- Tobias Smollett
✚ <i>Roderick</i> Hudson	- Henry James
✚ <i>Roderick</i>	- Robert Southey
✚ The <i>Lawless Roads</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Lawley Road</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ The <i>Road</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Finished Road</i>	- Ben Okri
✚ <i>Along the Road</i>	- A. L. Huxley
✚ The <i>Road</i> to Wigan Pier	- George Orwell
✚ The <i>Road</i> to Ruin	- Thomas Holcroft
✚ The <i>Road</i> to the Bazar	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The <i>Road</i> to Shimla	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The <i>Road</i> to Xanadu- A Study In The Ways of Imagination	- J. L. Lowes
✚ The <i>Road</i> Not Taken	- R. L. Frost
✚ An <i>Island Voyage</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ A <i>Sentimental Journey</i> Through France & Italy by Mr. Yorik	Laurence Sterne
-	
✚ <i>Journey</i> of the Magi	- T. S. Eliot
✚ A <i>Journey</i> from This World to the Next	- Henry Fielding
✚ <i>Journal</i> of a <i>Voyage</i> to Lisbon	- Henry Fielding
✚ A <i>New Voyage</i> Round the World	- Daniel Defoe
✚ <i>Gulliver's Travels</i>	- Jonathan Swift
✚ The <i>Voyage</i> Out	- Virginia Woolf
✚ <i>Amours De Voyage</i>	- A. H. Clough

✚ <i>Travels with My Aunt</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Travels with a Donkey in the Covenens</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ <i>The Unfortunate Traveller</i>	- Thomas Nashe
✚ <i>The Traveller</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ <i>The Longest Journey</i>	- E. M. Forster
✚ <i>Long Day's Journey into Night</i>	- Eugene O' Neill
✚ <i>Such a Long Journey</i>	- Rohinton Mistry
✚ <i>Journey without Maps</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>The Map-Maker</i>	- Keki N. Daruwalla
✚ <i>A Map of Misreading</i>	- Harold Bloom
✚ <i>The Map of Love</i>	- D. M. Thomas
✚ <i>New Maps of Hell</i>	- Kingsley Amis
✚ <i>The Poor House Fair</i>	- John (Hoyer) Updike
✚ <i>Bartholomew Fair</i>	- Ben Jonson
✚ <i>Bury Fair</i>	- Thomas Shadwell
✚ <i>Vanity Fair</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
✚ <i>The Vanity of the World</i>	- Matthew Prior
✚ <i>The Vanity of the Human Wishes</i>	- Dr. Johnson
✚ <i>A Passerby</i>	- Robert Bridges
✚ <i>Passerby</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>The Trespasser</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>No Thoroughfares</i>	- Charles Dickens & W. Collins
✚ <i>Thoroughfares</i>	- W. W. Gibson
✚ <i>A Way in the World</i>	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ <i>The Way We Live Now</i>	- Anthony Trollope
✚ <i>The Way to Win Him</i>	- G. Farquhar
✚ <i>The Way of the World</i>	- William Congreve
✚ <i>The Way of the World</i>	- Mirabell
✚ <i>The Way of All Flesh</i>	- Samuel Butler (1835-1902)

✚ The <i>Way</i> from Life to Death	- Walt Whitman
✚ The Highwayman	- Prof. Alfred Noyes
✚ Wayzgoose	- Roy Campbell
✚ The Castway	- William Cowper
✚ Ways of Escape	- Graham Greene
✚ The Great Indian Way	- Raja Rao
✚ The Zigzag Way	- Anita Desai
✚ Diana of the <i>Crossways</i>	- George Meredith
✚ <i>Diana</i>	- Henry Constable
✚ <i>Delia</i>	- Samuel Daniel
✚ <i>Crossways</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ A New Way to Pay Old Debts	- Philip Massinger
✚ The Middle <i>Passage</i>	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ Rites of <i>Passage</i>	- William Golding
✚ Rough <i>Passage</i>	- R. Parthasarthy
✚ Final <i>Passage</i>	- Caryl Phillips
✚ A <i>Passage</i> to England	- Nirad C. Chaudhary
✚ A <i>Passage</i> to India	- E. M. Forster
✚ <i>Passage</i> of India	- Walt Whitman
✚ The Patriot's <i>Progress</i>	- Henry Williamson
✚ Love's <i>Progress</i>	- John Donne
✚ The <i>Pilgrim</i> of Hope	- William Morris
✚ The <i>Pilgrim's Progress</i>	- John Bunyan
✚ Alma or the <i>Progress</i> of the Mind	- Matthew Prior
✚ Of the <i>Progress</i> of the Soul	- John Donne
✚ The <i>Progress</i> of Poesy	- Thomas Gray
✚ The Prince's <i>Progress</i> & Other Poems	- C. G. Rossetti
✚ The <i>Progress</i> of Error	- W. Cowper
✚ The <i>Error</i> of Alarm	- Harold Pinter
✚ <i>Vulgar Errors</i>	- Sir Thomas Browne

✚ These <i>Errors</i> are Correct	- Jeet Thayil
✚ <i>East</i> of Eden	- John Steinbeck
✚ <i>Eastern</i> Religion & <i>Western</i> Thought	- S. Radhakrishnsn
✚ Ballads of <i>East</i> & <i>West</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>East-West</i>	- Salman Rushdie
✚ The <i>Western</i> Canon	- Harold Bloom
✚ <i>North</i> of Boston	- R. L. Frost
✚ A Man from the <i>North</i>	- Arnold Bennett
✚ <i>North</i>	- Seamus Heaney
✚ The <i>North</i> Ship	- Philip Larkin
✚ <i>North</i> & <i>South</i>	- Mrs. E. C. Gaskell
✚ <i>East</i> Wind	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>West</i> Wind	- Pearl S. Buck
✚ <i>Daughter</i> of the <i>East</i>	- Benazir Bhutto
✚ <i>Eastward</i> Hoe !	- G. Chapman, Ben Jonson & Marston
✚ <i>Westward</i> Ho !	- Charles Kingsley
✚ <i>Westward</i> Hoe !	- John Webster & Dekker
✚ <i>Northward</i> Hoe !	- John Webster & Dekker
✚ The <i>Tower</i> of Silence	- Paul Scott
✚ The <i>Tower</i> of London	- W. H. Ainsworth
✚ The Constable of the <i>Tower</i>	-W. H. Ainsworth
✚ The <i>Tower</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ Two on a <i>Tower</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ The Two <i>Towers</i>	- J. R. R. Tolkien
✚ The Dark <i>Tower</i>	- Louis Macneice
✚ The <i>White</i> Man's Burden	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ The <i>White</i> Devil	- John Webster
✚ <i>White</i> Buildings	- Hart Crane
✚ Playing in the Dark: <i>Whiteness</i> and the Literary Imagination	- Toni Morrison

✚ The <i>White Peacock</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ The <i>White Monkey</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ The <i>White Tiger</i>	- Arvind Adiga
✚ The Ballad of <i>White Horse</i>	- G. K. Chesterton
✚ The <i>White Horseman</i>	- J. F. Hendry & H. Treece
✚ The Woman in <i>White</i>	- Wilkie Collins
✚ The <i>White Ship</i>	- D. G. Rossetti
✚ <i>White Jacket</i>	- Herman Melville
✚ The <i>White Doe of Rylstone</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ The <i>Black & White</i>	- Harold Pinter
✚ The <i>Black Skin & White Masks</i>	- Frantz Fanon
✚ The <i>Black Cottage</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ The <i>Black Arrow</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ <i>Black Boy</i>	- Richard Wright
✚ The Little <i>Black Boy</i>	- William Blake
✚ The <i>Black Prince</i>	- Miss Iris Murdoch
✚ The <i>Black Dwarf</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ <i>Black Eyed Susan</i>	- John Gay
✚ The Adventure of the <i>Black Lady</i>	- Mrs. Aphra Behn
✚ Across the <i>Black Waters</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Black Tower</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ Bye-Bye <i>Black Bird</i>	- Anita Desai
✚ A <i>Black Mischief</i>	- Evelyn Waugh
✚ <i>Black Venus</i>	- Angela Carter
✚ <i>Black Diaspora</i>	- Ronald Segal
✚ <i>Black Sheep</i>	- H. D. Balzac
✚ <i>Black Tulip</i>	- A. Dumas
✚ <i>Red & Black</i>	- Stendhal
✚ The Stars Turn <i>Red</i>	- Sean O' Casey
✚ <i>Red Roses for Me</i>	- Sean O'casey

+ Red Orleanders	- R. N. Tagore
+ The Red Wheel Barrow	- W. C. Williams
+ Portrait of a Man with Red Hair	- Hugh Walpole
+ Agnes Gray	- Anne Bronte
+ Vivian Grey	- Benjamin Disraeli
+ Lucy Gray	- William Wordsworth
+ Rosamund Gray	- Charles Lamb
+ The Picture of Dorian Gray	- Oscar Wilde
+ The Yellow Plush Correspondence	- W. M. Thackeray
+ Yellow book	- John Davidson
+ City of the Yellow Devil	- Maxim Gorky
+ The Pale Fire	- Vladimir Nabokov
+ The Man with the Blue Guitar	- Wallace Stevens
+ Love in Blue Time	- Hanif Khureshi
+ Arrow in the Blue	- Arthur Koestler
+ Blue Bird	- Maurice Macterlink
+ Girl in Blue	- P. G. Wodehouse
+ The Blue Umbrella	- Ruskin Bond
+ Purple Dust	- Sean O'casey
+ The Color Purple	- Alice Walker
+ The Purple Land That England Lost	- W. H. Hudson
+ England, Their England	- A. G. Macdonell
+ England, My England	- D. H. Lawrence
+ England, My England	- E. Henley
+ For England's Sake	- E. Henley
+ England Made Me	- Graham Greene
+ Ye Mariners of England	- Thomas Campbell
+ The Silver Spoon	- John Galsworthy
+ The Silver Box	- John Galsworthy

✚ The <i>Silver Tassie</i>	- Sean O' Casey
✚ The <i>Silver King</i>	- H. A. Jones
✚ The <i>Arrow of Gold</i>	- Joseph Conrad
✚ The <i>Golden Treasury of English Songs and Lyrics</i>	- F. Turner Palgrave
✚ <i>Golden Treasury of Indo- Anglican Poetry</i>	- V. K. Gokak
✚ A Goddess Named <i>Gold</i>	- Bhabhani Bhattacharya
✚ The Field of the Cloth of <i>Gold</i> or Darnley	- G. P. R. James
✚ The <i>Golden Honeycomb</i>	- Kamala Markandaya
✚ Their Very Own & <i>Golden City</i>	- Arnold Wesker
✚ Reflections on the <i>Golden Bed</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Golden Threshold</i>	- Sarojini Naidu
✚ The <i>Golden Notebook</i>	- Dorris May Lessing
✚ The <i>Golden Targe</i>	- William Dunbar
✚ The <i>Golden Bowl</i>	- Henry James
✚ The <i>Golden Gate</i>	- Vikram Seth
✚ The <i>Golden Breath</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ The <i>Golden Bough</i>	- Frazer
✚ The <i>Golden Broom</i>	- W. W. Gibson
✚ The <i>Golden Fleece</i>	- Robert Graves
✚ The <i>Golden Age</i>	- A. G. Gardiner
✚ The <i>Golden Chains</i>	- George Barker
✚ The <i>Golden Helm</i>	- W. W. Gibson
✚ <i>Gold Bat</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
✚ <i>Quality Street</i>	- Sir J. M. Barie
✚ <i>Mignel Street</i>	-V. S. Naipaul
✚ <i>Sinister Street</i>	- Sir Compton Mackenzie
✚ <i>Main Street</i>	- Harry Sinclair Lewis (First American Noble Laureate)
✚ <i>Grub Street</i>	- Henry Fielding
✚ <i>New Grub Street</i>	- G. Gissing
✚ The <i>Streets of London</i>	- John Gay

+ Cherry Orchard	- Anton Chekhov
+ Bells & Pomegranates	- Robert Browning
+ A House of Pomegranates	- Oscar Wilde
+ The Home & the World	- R. N. Tagore
+ Home & Beauty	- W. S. Maugham
+ Never at Home	- Dom Moraes
+ Home Coming	- C. P. Snow
+ The Home Coming	- Harold Pinter
+ Home Burial	- R. L. Frost
+ The Imaginary Home lands	- Salman Rushdie
+ The House Warning	- R. N. Tagore
+ The Hot House	- Harold Pinter
+ The Poorhouse Fair	- John (Hoyer) Updike
+ The House Holder	- R. P. Jhabvala
+ The Madras House	- H. G. Barker
+ To the Lighthouse	- Virginia Woolf
+ Cat on a Houseboat	- Anita Desai
+ Bleak House	- Charles Dickens
+ Open House	- J. B. Priestley
+ Farm House	- George Orwell
+ Glown's Houses	- Edith Sitwell
+ House Divided	- Pearl S. Buck
+ A House of Life	- D. G. Rossetti
+ The House of Fame	- G. Chaucer
+ The House of Fiction	- Henry James
+ The House of the Cawebs	- George Gissing
+ House of the Dead	- Fyodor Dostoevsky
+ The House of the Spirits	- Isabel Allende
+ Tiger in the House	- Ruskin Bond

✚ My Grandmother's <i>House</i>	- Kamala Das
✚ The <i>Widower's Houses</i>	-G. B. Shaw
✚ The <i>Widower's</i> Son	- Alan Silbitoe
✚ A <i>House</i> for Mr. <i>Biswas</i>	- V. S. Naipaul
✚ The Strange Case of Billy <i>Biswas</i>	- Arun Joshi
✚ In a <i>Balcony</i>	- Robert Browning
✚ The <i>Balconinny</i> & other Essays	- J. B. Priestley
✚ Casa Guidi <i>Windows</i>	- Elizabeth Barrett Browning
✚ High <i>Windows</i>	- Philip Larkin
✚ <i>Windows</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ On the <i>Knocking</i> at the Gate in Macbeth	- Thomas De Quincey
✚ I <i>Knock</i> at the Door	- Sean O'casey
✚ A <i>Room</i> with a View	- E. M. Forster
✚ Jacob's <i>Room</i>	-Virginia Woolf
✚ A <i>Room</i> of One's Own	- Virginia Woolf
✚ A <i>Room</i> at the Top	- John Braine
✚ <i>Room</i> on the Roof	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The Living <i>Room</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ The <i>Room</i>	-Harold Pinter
✚ The Dark <i>Room</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ Laughter in the Next <i>Room</i>	- Osbert Sitwell
✚ Barrack- <i>Room</i> Ballads	- Rudyard Kipling (First British Noble Laureate)
✚ The <i>Maid's</i> Tragedy	- Beaumont & Fletcher
✚ <i>Maid</i> Marian	- T. L. Peacock
✚ The Fair <i>Maid</i> of Perth	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The <i>Maiden</i> of the Mist	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ The <i>Merman</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ The <i>Mermaid</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ Come Down, O <i>Maid</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
✚ The Romantic Adventures of a <i>Milkmaid</i>	- Thomas Hardy

✚ <i>Love in Blue Time</i>	- Hanif Khureshi
✚ <i>The India I Love</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ <i>Love in a Tub</i>	- George Etherege
✚ <i>A Tale of a Tub</i>	- Ben Jonson
✚ <i>A Tale of a Tub</i>	- Jonathan Swift
✚ <i>The Professor</i>	- Charlotte Bronte
✚ <i>The Professor's Love Story</i>	- Sir J. M. Barrie
✚ <i>A Himalayan Love Story</i>	- Namita Gokhale
✚ <i>The Dance of Death</i>	- W. H. Auden
✚ <i>A Dance of the Forests</i>	- Wole Soyinka
✚ <i>Dance Like a Man</i>	- Mahesh Dattani
✚ <i>The Dance of the Eunuchs</i>	- Kamla Das
✚ <i>The Weird Dance</i>	- Chaman Nihal
✚ <i>A Time for Dance</i>	- C. Day Lewis
✚ <i>A Dance to the Music of Time</i>	- Anthony Powell
✚ <i>Court Dancer</i>	- R. N. Tagore
✚ <i>Michael Robartes & the Dancers</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>The Rose without a Thorn</i>	- Clifford Bax
✚ <i>Red Roses for Me</i>	- Sean O' Casey
✚ <i>The Policeman & the Rose</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ <i>The Two Rings</i>	- B. C. Chatterjee
✚ <i>The Rose & the Ring</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
✚ <i>The Ring & the Book</i>	- Robert Browning
✚ <i>The Lord of the Rings</i>	- J. R. R. Tolkein
✚ <i>The Secret Rose</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>The Rose</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>An Unofficial Rose</i>	- Miss Iris Murdoch
✚ <i>The Thistle & the Rose</i>	- W. Dunbar
✚ <i>Flags in the Dust</i>	- W. Faulkner
✚ <i>Put out More Flags</i>	- Evelyn Waugh

+ Put Yourself in His Place	- Charles Reade
+ Both Well	- A. C. Swinburne
+ You Can't Do Both	- Kingsley Amis
+ The <i>Bothic</i> of Tower-Na-Vuolich	- A. H. Clough
+ Take a Girl Like <i>You</i>	- Kingsley Amis
+ You Are Not Alone	- Miss Iris Murdoch
+ You Never Can Tell	- G. B. Shaw
+ Do What <i>You</i> Will	- A. Huxley
+ If <i>You're</i> Glad <i>I'll</i> Be Frank	- Tom Stofard
+ <i>I</i> Hear, It Was Charged Against <i>Me</i>	- Walt Whitman
+ <i>I</i> for One	- J. B. Priestley
+ If <i>I</i> May	- A. A. Milne
+ <i>I</i> Have Been Here Before	- J. B. Priestley
+ <i>I</i> Dare	- Kiran Bedi
+ If <i>I</i> Am Assassinated	- Z. A. Bhutto
+ If <i>I</i> Were <i>You</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
+ <i>Past & Present</i>	- Thomas Carlyle
+ Poems of the <i>Past & Present</i>	Thomas Hardy
+ The <i>Present</i> State of Polite Learning	- Oliver Goldsmith
+ Living in the <i>Present</i>	- John Wain
+ The <i>Nowhere</i> Man	- Kamala Markandaya
+ The <i>Nowhere</i> Man	- Pritish Nandy
+ The Kingdom of <i>Nowhere</i> - Utopia	- Thomas More
+ <i>Yet Again</i>	- Max Beerbohm
+ And <i>Even Now</i>	- Max Beerbohm
+ <i>Far Away & Long Ago</i>	- W. H. Hudson
+ <i>Delhi</i> is Not Far	- Ruskin Bond
+ In our <i>Time</i>	- Ernest Hemingway
+ Another <i>Time</i>	- W. H. Auden

✚ <i>Time of Hope</i>	- Sir C. P. Snow
✚ <i>Two Tramps in Mud Time</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ <i>Once Upon a Monsoon Time</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ <i>A Time for Dance</i>	- C. Day Lewis
✚ <i>A Dance to the Music of Time</i>	- Anthony Powell
✚ <i>Time & the Conways</i>	- J. B. Priestley
✚ <i>A Good Time was had by All</i>	- Steve Smith
✚ <i>A Time to Change</i>	- Nissim Ezekiel
✚ <i>A Matter of Time</i>	- Shashi Deshpandey
✚ <i>A Tale of the Time</i>	- Walt Whitman
✚ <i>A Time to be Happy</i>	- Nayantara Sehgal
✚ <i>Time Flies</i>	- C. G. Rossetti
✚ <i>Time Must Have a Stop</i>	- A. L. Huxley
✚ <i>Time & Tide</i>	- John Ruskin
✚ <i>Time Present</i>	- J. J. Osborne
✚ <i>The Bird of Time</i>	- Sarojini Naidu
✚ <i>Old Times</i>	- Harold Pinter
✚ <i>My Life & Times</i>	- V. V. Giri
✚ <i>Cocktail Time</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
✚ <i>Tracts for the Times</i>	- R. H. Froude
✚ <i>Hard Times</i>	- Charles Dickens
✚ <i>Hard Cash</i>	- Charles Kingsley
✚ <i>Time's Laughing Stocks</i>	- Thomas Hardy
✚ <i>The Time Machine</i>	- H. G. Wells
✚ <i>The Triumph of the Machine</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>The Triumph of Time</i>	- A. C. Swinburne
✚ <i>Ghosts in the Machine</i>	- Arthur Koestler
✚ <i>Nineteen Eighty Four</i>	- George Orwell
✚ <i>Nineteen Hundred & Nineteen</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>A Full Moon in the March</i>	- W. B. Yeats

✚ Saturday Night & Sunday Morning	- Alan Silbitoe
✚ The <i>Christian Year</i> @ Thoughts in Verse for the <i>Sundays</i> & Holydays Throughout the <i>Year</i>	- John Keble
✚ A Month of <i>Sundays</i>	- John (Hoyer) Updike
✚ Next <i>Sunday</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ <i>Sunday</i> at Hempstead	- James Thomson
✚ <i>Sunday</i> up the River	- James Thomson
✚ A Memory of Two <i>Mondays</i>	- Arthur Miller
✚ <i>Face</i> to <i>Face</i>	- Ved Prakash Mehta
✚ New Foes Within Old <i>Face</i>	- Charles Kingsley
✚ My True <i>Faces</i>	- Chaman Nihal
✚ <i>Facial</i> Justice	- L. P. Hartley
✚ <i>Faces</i>	- Walt Whitman
✚ <i>Morning Face</i>	- M. R. Anand
✚ <i>Morning Prayer</i>	- Nissim Ezekiel
✚ <i>Morning Raga</i>	- Mahesh Dattani
✚ Great <i>Morning</i>	- Osbert Sitwell
✚ Mr. <i>Noon</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ A Still <i>Afternoon</i>	- D. H. Lawrence
✚ <i>Afternoon</i>	- Harold Pinter
✚ Death in the <i>Afternoon</i>	- Ernest Hemingway
✚ A Hot <i>Noon</i> in Malabar	- Kamla Das
✚ From <i>Noon</i> to Starry <i>Night</i>	- Walt Whitman
✚ <i>Evening</i> in Byzantium	- Irwin Shaw
✚ Jocelyn	- John Galsworthy
✚ <i>Evelina</i>	- Fanny Burney
✚ <i>Eve</i> & other Poems	- Ralph Hodgson
✚ An <i>Evening</i> Walk	- W. Wordsworth
✚ It is a Beauteous <i>Evening</i> , Calm & Free	- W. Wordsworth
✚ Lines on an Autumnal <i>Evening</i>	- S. T. Coleridge

✚ Stopping By Woods on a <i>Snowy Evening</i>	- R. L. Frost
✚ <i>Ancient Evenings</i>	- Norman Mailer
✚ <i>Socialite Evenings</i>	- Shobha De
✚ <i>The Eve of St. John</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ <i>The Eve of St. Agnes</i>	- John Keats
✚ <i>The Eve of Saint Mark</i>	- John Keats
✚ <i>Eve's Ransom</i>	- George Gissing
✚ <i>Evelyn's Innes</i>	- George Moore
✚ <i>Tintern Abbey</i>	- William Wordsworth
✚ <i>Westminster Abbey</i>	- Matthew Arnold
✚ <i>Northanger Abbey</i>	- Jane Austen
✚ <i>Nightmare Abbey</i>	- T. L. Peacock
✚ <i>The Nightrunners of Bengal</i>	- John Masters
✚ <i>Arabian Nights</i>	- Sir Richard Burton
✚ <i>New Arabian Nights</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ <i>Starry Nights</i>	- Shobha De
✚ <i>Night of the Leopard</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ <i>Night Train at Deoli</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ <i>Thieves in the Night</i>	- Arthur Koestler
✚ <i>Midsummer's Night Dream</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ <i>The Complaint or Night Thoughts on Life</i>	- Edward Young
✚ <i>Twelfth Night</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ <i>The City of Dreadful Night</i>	- James Thomson
✚ <i>A Night of the Trojan War</i>	- John Drinkwater
✚ <i>The Fine Summer Night</i>	- M. Arnold
✚ <i>A Southern Night</i>	- Matthew Arnold
✚ <i>Frost at Midnight</i>	- S. T. Coleridge
✚ <i>Music at Night</i>	- Aldous Huxley
✚ <i>Music at Night</i>	- J. B. Priestley

✚ Witches & Other <i>Night Fears</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ Islands <i>Nights Entertainment</i>	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ The Mistakes of a <i>Night</i>	- Oliver Goldsmith
✚ Full <i>Moon</i>	- P. G. Wodehouse
✚ Crescent <i>Moon</i>	- R. N. Tagore
✚ The <i>Moonstone</i>	- Wilkie Collins
✚ The Panther's <i>Moon</i>	- Ruskin Bond
✚ The <i>Moon & Six Pence</i>	- W. S. Maugham
✚ The <i>Moon</i> is Down	- John Steinbeck
✚ The First Man in the <i>Moon</i>	- H. G. Wells
✚ The Man in the <i>Moon</i>	- Drayton
✚ The Man in the <i>Moon</i>	- John Lyly
✚ The Woman in the <i>Moon</i>	- John Lyly
✚ The Cat & the <i>Moon</i>	- W. B. Yeat
✚ A Full <i>Moon</i> in the March	- W. B. Yeats
✚ The Middle <i>March</i>	- George Eliot
✚ Triumphant <i>March</i>	- T. S. Eliot
✚ On <i>Nothing</i> , on <i>Something</i> , on <i>Everything</i>	- Hillaire Belloc
✚ <i>Nothing & Loving</i>	- Henry Green (H.V.Yorke)
✚ To Say <i>Nothing</i> of the Dog	- J. K. Jerome
✚ Much Ado About <i>Nothing</i>	- W. Shakespeare
✚ Losers take All	- Graham Greene
✚ Winner take <i>Nothing</i>	- Ernest Hemingway
✚ <i>Nothing</i> Good Can Stay	- R. L. Frost
✚ Money for <i>Nothing</i>	-P.G. Wodehouse
✚ <i>Nothing</i> Serious	- P. G. Wodehouse
✚ <i>Something</i> to Answer for	- P. H. Newby
✚ <i>Something</i> of Myself	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ Chips with <i>Everything</i>	- Arnold Wesker
✚ After <i>Democracy</i>	- H. G. Wells

+ <i>Yesterday & Today</i>	- K. P. S. Menon
+ <i>Twenty Years After</i>	- Alexander Dumas
+ <i>After Many a Summer</i>	- Aldous Huxley
+ <i>After Strange Gods</i>	- T. S. Eliot
+ <i>Grace After Meal</i>	- J. C. Ransom
+ <i>After the Funeral</i>	- D. M. Thomas
+ <i>Death & After</i>	- Annie Besant
+ <i>After the Fall</i>	- Arthur Miller
+ <i>The Two Races of Man- Lender & Borrower</i>	- Charles Lamb
+ <i>The Thores of Democracy</i>	- Walt Whitman
+ <i>Two Cheers of Democracy</i>	- K. R. S. Iyengar
+ <i>Two Cheers of Democracy</i>	- E. M. Forster
+ <i>After Democracy</i>	- H. G. Wells
+ <i>The Two Drovers</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
+ <i>Poems by Two Brothers</i>	- A. L. Tennyson
+ <i>The Two Chiefs of Dunboy</i>	- J. A. Froude
+ <i>The Two Paths</i>	- John Ruskin
+ <i>The Two Nations</i>	- Benjamin Disraeli
+ <i>Two Years Ago</i>	- Charles Kingsley
+ <i>No Second Troy</i>	- W. B. Yeats
+ <i>The Three Voices of Poetry</i>	- T. S. Eliot
+ <i>Three Years She Grew</i>	- William Wordsworth
+ <i>Three Musketeers</i>	- Alexander Dumas
+ <i>Three Sisters</i>	- Anton Chekhov
+ <i>The Third</i>	- Nissim Ezekiel
+ <i>The Third Man</i>	- Graham Greene
+ <i>Soldiers Three</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
+ <i>The Soldier</i>	- Rupert Brooke
+ <i>Soldiers Pay</i>	- W. Faulkner

✚ Into <i>Battle</i>	- Charles Sorley
✚ Into the <i>Battle</i>	- Winston Churchill
✚ Get Ready for <i>Battle</i>	- R. P. Jhabvala
✚ The <i>Battle of the Books</i>	- Jonathan Swift
✚ <i>Tale of Modern India</i>	- Raja Rao
✚ <i>A Tale of Two Cities</i>	- Charles Dickens
✚ <i>Tales of Three Cities</i>	- Henry James
✚ <i>A Tale of the Time</i>	- Walt Whitman
✚ <i>The Handmaid's Tale</i>	- Margaret Atwood
✚ <i>The Handmaid's Tale</i>	- Harold Pinter
✚ <i>Tales of Mermaid Tavern</i>	- Prof. Alfred Noyes
✚ <i>A Tale of a Tub</i>	- Ben Jonson
✚ <i>A Tale of a Tub</i>	- Jonathan Swift
✚ <i>The Old Wives Tale</i>	- George Peele
✚ <i>The Old Wives Tale</i>	- Arnold Bennett
✚ <i>Tales from Shakespeare</i>	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>Tales of Sherlock Holmes</i>	- Sir A. C. Doyle
✚ <i>Tales of My Landlord</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ <i>Tales of the Crusaders</i>	- Sir Walter Scott
✚ <i>Grandmother's Tale</i>	- R. K. Narayan
✚ <i>My Grandmother's House</i>	- Kamla Das
✚ <i>The Four Ages of Poetry</i>	- T. L. Peacock
✚ <i>The Four Ages of Man</i>	- W. B. Yeats
✚ <i>The Four Georges</i>	- W. M. Thackeray
✚ <i>The Four Hymns</i>	- Spenser
✚ <i>The Four Beauties</i>	- H. E. Bates
✚ <i>Four Portraits</i>	- Peter Quennell
✚ <i>The Five Nations</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>The Seven Seas</i>	- Rudyard Kipling
✚ <i>Susanna's Seven Husbands</i>	- Ruskin Bond

+ Seven Against Thebes	- Aeschylus
+ Dance of Seven Deadly Sins	-William Dunbar
+ In the <i>Seven Woods</i>	- W. B. Yeats
+ The <i>Seven Lamps of Architecture</i>	-John Ruskin
+ The <i>Seven Stone of Venice</i>	- John Ruskin
+ The <i>Seven Pillars of Wisdom</i>	- T. E. Lawrence
+ <i>Seven Circles Round the Fire</i>	-Mahesh Dattani
+ <i>Seven Types of Ambiguity</i>	- William Empson
+ <i>Seven Principles of Man</i>	- Annie Besant
+ (7) Aspects of the Novel	- E. M. Forster
+ We are <i>Seven</i>	- William Wordsworth
+ <i>Thirteenth Sun</i>	- Amrita Pritam
+ Vivat !, Vivat !, Regina !	- R. O. Bolt
+ Pioneers ! O Pioneers !	- Walt Whitman
+ O Captain ! My Captain !	- Walt Whitman
+ Provide ! Provide !	- R. L. Frost
+ The Sea , the Sea	- Irish Murdoch
+ <i>Absalom, Absalom</i>	- W. Faulkner
+ <i>Absalom & Achitophel</i>	- John Dryden
+ Fasting, Feasting	- Anita Desai
+ <i>Poetical Sketches</i>	- William Blake
+ <i>Descriptive Sketches</i>	- William Wordsworth
+ <i>Scenes from a Writer's Life</i>	- Ruskin Bond
+ <i>Scenes of Clerical Life</i>	- George Eliot
+ <i>Morte De Arthur</i> (1470)	- Sir Thomas Malory
+ <i>Morte D' Arthur</i> (1842)	- A. L. Tennyson
+ <i>Don Quixote</i>	- Miguel De Cervantes
+ <i>Don Juan</i>	- Lord Byron
+ <i>Don Carlos</i>	- Thomas Otway

+ Don Sebastian	- John Dryden
+ The School Mistress	- A. W. Pinero
+ The School Mistress	- W. Shenstone
+ The School Master	- Roger Ascham
+ The Old & the New School Master	- Charles Lamb
+ Mr. Leicester's School	- Charles Lamb
+ The School of Abuse	- Stephen Gosson
+ The School of Shooting	- Roger Ascham
+ The School for Scandal	- R. B. Sheridan
+ Men, Women & Books	- Leigh Hunt
+ Familiar Studies of Men & Books	- R. L. Stevenson
+ The Book of the Duchess	- G. Chaucer
+ King's Quair Book	- James I
+ The Book of Colyn Clout	- J. Skeleton
+ Book of Philip Sparrow	- J. Skeleton
+ Book of the Sword	- Sir Richard Burton
+ Book of Martyrs	- John Foxe
+ The Battle of the Books	- J. Swift
+ The Book of Urizen	- William Blake
+ The Book of Los	- William Blake
+ The Book of Thel	- William Blake
+ The Bride's Book of Beauty	- M. R. Anand
+ The Books in My Life	- Henry Miller
+ The Book Kerith	- George Moore
+ A Book of Verse	- E. Henley
+ The Book of Snobs	- W. M. Thackeray
+ The Book of Cerm	- Robert Buchnan
+ Book of Faith	- Reginald Peacock
+ The Faithful Shepherdess	- Fletcher
+ Lack Shepherd	- W. H. Ainsworth

✚ Sad <i>Shepherd</i>	- Ben Jonson
✚ The <i>Wooden</i> Shepherdes	- Richard Hughes
✚ A <i>Chapter</i> on Dreams	- R. L. Stevenson
✚ A <i>Chapter</i> on Ears	- Charles Lamb
✚ <i>End</i> of a <i>Chapter</i>	- John Galsworthy
✚ The Sense of an <i>Ending</i>	- Julian Barnes
✚ The Sense of <i>Ending</i> - Studies in the Theory of Fiction	- J. F. Kermode
✚ The <i>End</i> of the <i>Affair</i>	- Graham Greene
✚ <i>Ends</i> & <i>Means</i>	- Aldous Huxley
✚ Howard's <i>End</i>	- E. M. Forster
✚ London <i>End</i>	- J. B. Priestley
✚ The <i>End</i> of the <i>World</i>	- Gordon Bottomley
✚ The <i>End</i> of the <i>World</i>	- Lascelles Abercrombie

Suggestions for Further Research:-

- The researcher can enlist often repeated *Characters* in different literary works.
- The researcher can enlist the names of *Main Literary Authors* often confused by readers such as Ben Jonson, Dr. Johnson, Samuel Butler (Restoration), Samuel Butler (Victorian) etc...

References:

Arora, Dr. Sudhir K. , "A Handbook of Language and Literature for Competitive Examinations- PGT/TGT", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., Reprint-2012, ISBN-978-81-7977-419-9

- Bansal, Sanjeev Kumar, "A Unique Collection of Literary Works Often Confused (Part-I)",
 Aarhat Multidisciplinary International Education Research Journal (AMIERJ),
 Bi-Monthly, Peer-Reviewed Journal, ISSN-2278-5655, Volume-I, Issue-II,
 Apr/May 2013 issue, Page Nos.-47-74
- Daiches, David. A Critical History of English Literature. New Delhi: Allied Publishers Pvt.
 Limited, 1979; rpt. 2005.
- Jain, Dr. B.B., "UGC NET/JRF/SET, English Paper-II", Upkar Prakashan, Agra-2, U.P., Pages-
 132, ISBN-978-81-7482-875-0, Code No.-940
- Jain, Dr. B.B., "UGC NET/JRF/SET, English Paper-III", Upkar Prakashan, Agra-2, U.P., Pages-
 184, ISBN-978-81-7482-419-6, Code No.-1544
- Kumar, Satish & Bansal, Anupama; "A History of English Literature- From the Age of Chaucer
 to the Age of Twentieth Century", Lakshmi Narain Agarwal, Agra, U.P., ISBN-
 81-85778-70-1
- Mundra & Mundra, J.N.,S.C.; "A History of English Literature-Vol-I- Anglo-Saxon Period to the
 Age of Dryden", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., 2011, Pages 464, ISBN
 (Vol-I) -978-81-7977-251-5 , ISBN-Set-978-81-7977-254-6
- Mundra & Mundra, J.N.,S.C.; "A History of English Literature-Vol-II- The Age of Pope to the
 Romantic Period ", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., Reprint-2005, Pages 542,
 ISBN (Vol-II) -81-85897-38-7 , ISBN-Set-81-85897-36-0
- Mundra & Mundra, J.N., S.C.; "A History of English Literature- Vol-III- The Victorian Age to
 the Present Day ", Prakash Book Depot, Bareilly, U.P., Reprint-2004, Pages 730,
 ISBN-Set-81-85897-36-0
- "Objective English", Pratiyogita Sahitya Series, Sahitya Bhavan, Agra, U.P., Pages 290 , Code-
 953
- Sachdeva, S.K., "Year Book ", Competition Success Review, New Delhi, 1998 , Pp 876,
 P.No.453-468
- Tetarwal, C.R., "UGC-NET English Objective Solved Papers", Amar Ujala Publications Ltd.,
 Noida, U.P., 2012, Pages 226
- Verma, A.S., "UGC: NET/ SLET English Paper-II", Pratiyogita Sahitya Series, Sahitya Bhavan,
 Agra, U.P., Code-A500